

Protecting FPC from Overheating Using Coating

Hani Alkhatib ¹

For the degree in MSc Energy

School of Engineering and Physical Sciences, Heriot-Watt University

Supervisor: Dr. Tadhg S. O'Donovan

Abstract

Flat plate solar collector is the main part of a solar heating system, the collector absorbs sun radiation and transforms it into heat then transfer the heat to the fluid inside the collector, which can be used in many applications either in industry or normal households. One of the biggest problems that faces the FPC is overheating. This research introduces a way to reduce the effect of overheating on the absorber plate and lower the stagnation temperature using coating that is applied on the external side of the glass cover, the coating which is used with the collector reduces the solar irradiance coming through by blocking all the Ultraviolet (UV) waves and transmits only 70% from visible light waves and 70% from infrared waves which will reject up to 38% of solar energy. The efficiency of the solar collector is analyzed and measured before and after applying the coating experimentally and theoretically using a system which was built on the roof of Heriot Watt University and a software called CoDePro. The efficiency in different flow rates and the stagnation temperature was analyzed experimentally and theoretically. Experimentally, the starting efficiency dropped 15% on average after the coating. meanwhile, the stagnation temperature decreased 19% from 132.29° C to 108.7 ° C. Theoretically, the starting efficiency dropped 21% on average and the stagnation temperate decreased by 19.32%. Also, there was a good agreement between the numerical result and the experimental result.

Keywords: Flat Plate Collector (FPC), Overheating, Coating, Platinum Silver 70.

¹ Email address: ha107@hw.ac.uk ID: H00130460 MSc Energy

Table of Contents

Abstract	I
1. Introduction.....	3
1.1. Flat plate solar collector systems	4
1.2. Solar radiation	5
1.3. Flow configuration.....	6
1.4. Absorber plate	6
1.5. Glazing.....	6
1.6. Coating.....	6
1.7. Overheating.....	7
1.8 project aims and thesis organization	8
2. Apparatus and Methods	9
2.1 LabVIEW Code.....	10
2.2 Experimental Tests	11
2.2.1 Data collection and system setup.....	11
2.2.2 Efficiency test with different flow rates.....	12
2.2.3 Overheating test	13
2.2.4 Platinum Silver 70 Coating.....	13
2.3 Theoretical Tests	14
2.3.1 CoDePro.....	14
2.3.2 MATLAB.....	15
3. Result	16
3.1. Experimental tests.....	16
3.1.1. Before Applying the Coating.....	16
3.1.2. After Applying the Coating	18
3.2. Theoretical results.....	20
3.2.1. Before the Coating	21
3.2.2. After the coating	21
4. Discussion.....	23
5. Conclusion	26
Appendix.....	27
References.....	30

1. Introduction

As the old energy sources are limited and can't meet the expanding demand of energy, also with the increasing prices of fuel and CO₂ emissions, wide use of the renewable energy technologies such as solar collectors is the way to go, also providing hot water using cheap reliable and emissions-free to domestic and industrial level is very important.

Solar collector is special kind of heat exchangers that can transform irradiance into heat, the radiation coming from the sun can be used as renewable and clean energy source, when the radiation hits the absorber plate it transforms to heat and the heat is used to heat the fluid, and this heated fluid is mostly used as a domestic hot water in houses. This fluid is put in pipes and tanks to protect them from pollutants, and because of the increasing price of oil, using solar heating system is increasing as they can cover 25% of household energy consumption. (Kalogirou, S.A. 2004))

There are four types of solar collector technologies each can be used in different application depending on the efficiency and the different temperature that each type can handle (John, A. and William, A, 2013)

(Vijay et al. 2013) reviewed different types of solar collector with different applications and analyzed their performances and the FPC was the best for household applications. Flat plate solar collectors (FPC) are very widely used because they are simple and it's a well-developed technology, also it requires very little maintenance and uses direct and diffused radiation (John, A. and William, A, 2013).

Flat plate solar collector is the most used technology among all other solar technologies, they have very good efficiency and excellent potential for domestic and industrial applications that's the main reason to why they are more attractive than other technologies, it is important to have a reliable solar collector with long life expectancy, it is critical to solve most common and dangerous problems that might face the solar collector to increase their life expectancy and avoid efficiency drop during their life time. Overheating is the number one most dangerous problem that faces the FPC, effecting their performance and life expectancy of the system. (Elimar Frank, Franz Mauthner, Stephan Fischer, 2015)

1.1. Flat plate solar collector systems

There are two main type of systems of FPC which are used in demotic applications, the first type is passive system and the second type is active system which will be used in the experiment on the roof. As can be seen in the schematic drawing in figure (1), the system used is an active non pressurized system consisting of the following components: thermocouples (K-type), flow meter, valves, pyranometer, filter, FPC and water tank.

Figure (1): Schematic diagram of the FPC system on the roof.

The flat plate solar collector itself consists of 5 main parts: cover strip, header and riser, insulation (on bottom and on the sides) and absorber plate all we be covered in the main box as can be seen in figure (1) (Ruzhu and Xiaoqiang, 2018).

Rate of extraction from the collector can be measured as follows (Imants and Liene, 1995):

$$Q_u = Q_i - Q_o = m C_p \Delta T \quad (1)$$

Where m is the mass flow rate in kg/s and C_p is the heat capacity in J/K° and ΔT is the temperature difference between inlet fluid and the outlet fluid in K° or C°.

The amount of solar radiation received by the FPC can be expressed as: (Fabio Struckmann, 2008)

$$Q_i = I \cdot A \quad (2)$$

Where I is the intensity of solar radiation W/m² and A is the collector surface area in m².

The heat characteristics equation can also be expressed in equation (3) as: (John, A. and William, A, 2013)

$$Q = A_c G \left(\eta_0 - a_1 \frac{(T_m - T_a)}{G} - a_2 \frac{(T_m - T_a)^2}{G} \right) \quad (3)$$

A measure of a flat plate collector performance is the collector efficiency (η) and it is known as useful energy (Q_u) takings over the accruing solar radiation over specific period of time (A.Whillier,1953).

$$\mu = \frac{\int Q_u dt}{A \int I dt} = \frac{m C_p \Delta T}{A.I} \quad (4)$$

1.2. Solar radiation

Solar radiation coming from the sun to hit the earth has a wavelength between $0.3 \mu\text{m} < \lambda < 2.5 \mu\text{m}$ which is divided into three categories which are: Ultraviolet (UV) waves, Visible light and Infrared waves (John, A. and William, A, 2013), some of the solar radiation gets absorbed by the atmosphere the rest will pass and hit the solar collector then it will be absorbed by the absorber plate which will transform it to heat and transfer it to the fluid passing in the tubes, controlling the amount of the radiation and the wavelengths which will be absorbed by the solar plate is a good approach to solve the overheating problem (Alkhatib, 2025; Alkhatib et al., 2021, 2023a, 2023c, 2023d, 2023b, 2024; Alkhatib, Norton, et al., 2025; Alkhatib, O’Neill, et al., 2025; Alkhatib & Lemarchand, 2025; Omar et al., 2025).

Energy loss in FPC can occur by conduction, convection and radiation, and can be illustrate by thermal network diagram to make the analyzation process easier as can be seen in Figure (2) (Paone et al. 2014), the diagram consists of 4 main areas (Glass, Coating, Absorber plate and insulation) that can be modified to protect the FPC from overheating.

Figure (2): Thermal network diagram of the FPC (Paone et al. 2014).

1.3. Flow configuration

The flow configuration is very critical when it comes to designing the FPC, the FPC consists from header and riser, controlling the volumetric flow rate and flow distribution has a huge effect on the performance of the flat plate collector (Duffie and Beckman 2006), having an ununiform flow can reduce the efficiency significantly and can damage the solar collector, also will make it overheat faster which will even cause more damage, the flow distribution depends on header shape, inlet manifold, outlet manifold....etc. all these factors must be chosen carefully to maximize the efficiency of the solar collector and to prevent it from overheating (Facao 2015).

1.4. Absorber plate

Absorber plate is used to increase the entropy and it works by transforming the energy from the solar radiation into heat and send it to the fluid inside the tubes.

Flat plate solar collector usually consists of parallel pipes which are welded onto the absorber plate, absorber plate is usually copper or aluminum (the one on the roof is copper), the upper side of the absorber plate is high absorbance for radiation and the lower part has insulation material. (Jilani and Thomas 2014)

The absorber plate is the most sensitive part in the FPC that will suffer serios damage during overheating, the elasticity of the absorber plate will change, and the physical properties will change which will lower the life expectancy and the efficiency of the FPC.

1.5. Glazing

Normal glass is usually used with FPC it has refractive index of 1.526 and can transmit up to 0.891 of the solar spectrum, the system that is used in this dissertation is using single glass FPC with long wave absorbance of 0.88 (Kalogirou, S.A.,2004).

(Vaibhav Singh et al. 2018) concluded that the higher the transmissivity of the glass and the coating the more heat will pass and will be absorbed by the absorber plate and the higher the temperature difference between the inlet and the outlet and changing the transmissivity is a good approach to solve the overheating problem. (Akhtar and Mullick 1999), (Akhtar and Mullick 2007) came up with an easy procedure to calculate the heat transfer across the glass either double or single glass under certain conditions and concluded that the performance of FPC can be enhanced by adding the right coating on the glass also to protect from overheating, coating that will lower the heat coming from the sun should be chosen and should be place on the external section of the glass which will filter the solar spectrum controlling which wavelengths should pass. (Paone et al. 2014).

1.6. Coating

Selective coating improves the overall performance of the FPC and can be used to solve particular problems, a lot of the coating used in cold weather is to increase the absorbance from the sun to give more energy to the fluid passing through the pipes, on the other hand in hot weather areas like

UAE, coating that will decrease the energy absorbed is needed because of the overheating problem. (Wu et al. 2013)

Although the efficiency of the solar collector is relatively high, and provide high potential, but at low irradiance weather the FPC has low efficiency and coating is used to absorb heat and store it. On the other hand, in high irradiance weather, the FPC the efficiency drop because of the overheating and might need coating to protect it from overheating that might occur. (Resch et al. 2008)

1.7. Overheating

Overheating happens when a lot of heat is collected with no demand which means that the water will keep on heating up until and the system temperature exceeds the operating temperature and reaches a maximum temperature which is called stagnation temperature, overheating and stagnation are the most important problems facing the solar collector and they are significant factors in measuring the installation's useful life, overheating can also happen when the heat transfer through the fluid is stopped because of power outage or component failure this will develop stagnations.

Overheating is very common in hot weather just like UAE, the extremely hot weather can heat the water very fast and can make the system reach the stagnation temperature very fast.

Polymeric materials are used in a lot in solar energy systems particularly in domestic hot water applications (DHW) because it's very efficient in low temperature applications, these materials are used a lot in FPC because it reduces the cost and uses the solar energy, the maximum temperature needed in DHW applications is about 80° C, but the FPC can reach up to 200° C while overheating, which is higher than the working temperature of plastics (80-140° C), this will cause irreversible deformation and decaying which will change the physical properties and lower the overall performance (Resch et al. 2008, Ehrmann et al. 2013).

In pressurized systems the overheating damage will be huge to the system because the pipes will start leaking or the pressure relief valve will remove all the fluid from the system which will cost a lot to refill the system (especially if the fluid was not water).

(Elimar Frank, Franz Mauthner, Stephan Fischer, 2015) Concluded that overheating damage is huge and can damage other parts of the system such as:

- 1- The pumping system.
- 2- The absorber coating.
- 3- pipes and collector (Permanent deformation will occur).
- 4- The rubber seals in the piping system.
- 5- leakages of the high temperature fluids which can harm humans.

Other systems use costly equipment such as expansion vessel and pressure relief valve, not only these are expensive but also, they are energy waste full, and putting them in every system is not practical and will increase the maintenance needed. (J.P. Roberts,2000) (Spychaj 2012).

(Stephens, R.B., 1981) used particles solubility to regulate the heat collected, the problem with this system is that the light waves are still being absorbed to a certain extent, so the thermal efficiency of the optical switch is reduced, unlike (Slaman and Griessen 2009) which uses Prismatic structures which is a structure that can switch to reflect the light and work with a fluid that will be put under the glass structure, in spite of the fact that the system is inexpensive but to make the fluid work well with the structure it should be in the right index when evaporated which is not easy to do in systems, also pumping the fluid in and maintain it in the right pressure is costly.

(Wallner et al. 2008) and (Weber et al. 2014) used thermotropic glazing to protect the FPC from overheating which performed good under certain weather, but the expected life time of it is low and some types has low operating temperature which will not work properly in UAE's weather.

1.8 project aims and thesis organization

The FPC used in UAE can suffer from overheating very rapidly on daily passes which will result in significant damage to the FPC system, this considered a challenge for users to protect their FPC system with a cheap and reliable method.

In view of the above, methods that can work properly with hot weather and can be easily commercialized is needed, all of the previous approaches made to solve the overheating problem was either costly or not applicable in hot weather and some was not practical.

The main aims of this paper are to Find a suitable coating that will reduce the stagnation temperature, testing the validity of the coating experimentally and theoretically and finally analyzing and comparing the result on multiple software (MATLAB and CoDePre). To achieve these objectives, this paper is divided to 5 parts as below:

Part (1): introduction to the paper topic and literature review to summarize other researchers' achievements in FPC overheating area.

Part (2): Methodology used to achieve the protection wanted for the FPC including choosing the coating, testing the coating experimentally, simulating the performance of the coating using software and validating the result.

Part (3): The results obtained from the FPC system tests including efficiency with different scenarios and the stagnation temperature also the results obtained from the simulation software and the system response.

Part (4): Further analysis to the result in Part (3) will be discussed to know why the system reacted in specific way and how the coating achieved the goals, also to know how close the numerical simulation to the actual result was.

Part (5): Conclusion to the paper.

2. Apparatus and Methods

For the coating to work perfectly it must lower the stagnation temperature and prevent the overheating from happening or reduce the damage of the overheating.

The methodology used in the dissertation has focused on finding the simplest type of coating which will be effective and inexpensive, it must be easy to apply on the glass also and can work effectively in hot and humid weather like UAE's weather.

The best approach is consisted of two main sections, testing the coating experimentally and numerically. By testing the coating experimentally, the applicability of the coating in real life during hot weather will be known and the capability for commercialization will be known as well and to further examination and to validate the previous result a numerically approach is needed.

The methods adopted were as follows:

- To narrow the scope of the dissertation, the key factors that effects the overheating was identified and measured.
- Coating that can be applies easily and will be effective theoretically and experimentally was chosen.
- Building a code on LabVIEW to be able to take measurement correctly from the sensors with the correct scale.
- Testing the coating experimentally by building a complete FPC system on the HWU roof and taking the necessary measurements.
- The FPC first test was done by running the system with different flow rates before and after the coating, to see how the whole system will react to the change with coating and if the efficiency will change.
- Doing the overheating test on the system for 3 straight days twice (before and after applying the coating) to check changes on the stagnation temperature of the FPC and how the system will react.
- Experimental data was filtered, organized and analyzed to a tangible set of data.
- Build MATLAB code to represent the Data and compare the scenarios.
- Applying the same tests on CoDePro software to get the theoretical result and compare it with the experimental result.

2.1 LabVIEW Code

LabVIEW software was used to read the measurements from the sensors and convert the voltage coming out to a sensible data. First, the code was made as can be seen in Figure (3), it has a while loop to keep the code running and to protect it, a DAQ assistant was used to organize the channels change the scale so it will convert the readings into sensible data, output graphs was used to make graphs representations for the signals, there are also unit conversion blocks to convert the volumetric flow rate and average blocks to take average for the solar irradiance.

Figure (3): LabVIEW code created.

All the DAQ channels were connected through wires into the laptop in right order and were scaled correctly to be able to recode reasonable data in the specified file location using file path, after that the wires were connected into the right measurement sensor.

2.2 Experimental Tests

2.2.1 Data collection and system setup.

The system built on the roof has the following components:

- 1- Main component which are:
 - a. A small sized FPC (130 cm X 116 cm).
 - b. Small water tank.
 - c. Pips, connections and valves.
 - d. Pressure relief valve.
 - e. Pumps.
 - f. Filter.
- 2- Secondary components:
 - a. Thermocouples.
 - b. Flow meter.
 - c. Pyranometer.
 - d. cDAQ from national instruments.
 - e. LabVIEW software.
 - f. Wires and NI-cDAQ.

System was built, cleaned, repaired and tested to make sure everything is working correctly as can be seen in Figure (4).

Figure (4): FPC system on the roof.

Two main experiments were done on this system to test the performance of the coating, but before that the following constant factors were measured:

- 1- Incident angle of beam radiation.
- 2- Collector slope.
- 3- Collector dimensions and absorber dimensions to calculate the gross area.
- 4- Cover material data (glass and coating).
- 5- Plate thickness and material type.
- 6- Insulation U-value.
- 7- Tubes dimensions and number.

2.2.2 Efficiency test with different flow rates

First test was performed by running the system normally and measuring the efficiency of the FPC, three different flow rates were tested on the system before applying the coating and after applying it.

Table (1): Efficiency test description.

Efficiency test with different flow rates	
Frequency of the measurements	One reading every one second
Data collected	1- Ambient temperature. 2- Solar irradiance. 3- Inlet and outlet temperatures. 4- Volumetric flow rate.
Important Factors Calculated	1- Efficiency. 2- Heat output. 3- Mass flow rate.
Important Graphs Made	Efficiency curve based on temperature difference to find the efficiency equation.
Duration of the test	1-2 hours

The test was made three times before applying the coating with three different flow rates (high, medium and low flow rates), then the coating was applied, and the test was repeated 3 times with the same three flow rates.

2.2.3 Overheating test

Second test was done by closing the inlet of the FPC, leaving the outlet open and switching off the pump, also an extra thermocouple was added on the absorber plate to measure the stagnation temperature of the system, the test was performed for three straight days without the coating and was repeated for another 3 days after applying the coating.

Table (2): Overheating test description.

Overheating test	
Frequency of the measurements	One reading every 10 seconds
Data collected	1- Ambient temperature. 2- Solar irradiance. 3- Inlet and outlet temperatures. 4- Volumetric flow rate. 5- Absorber plate temperature
Important Factors Calculated	Stagnation Temperature
Important Graphs Made	The overheating graph
Duration of the test	72 hours

2.2.4 Platinum Silver 70 Coating

Platinum Silver 70 (PP 70) was applied on the external side of the FPC's glass cover using a certain tools and Technique to make sure the coating is applied correctly with no bubbles or gaps between the glass cover and the Platinum Silver 70 coating.

PP70 is cheap, easy to apply, does not change the look of the FPC and has a good potential to reduce the solar energy absorbed by the absorber plate in the overheating scenario, also the PP70 add an extra layer of protection to the glass cover of the PFC which will protect the glass cover from scratches and break, most importantly the coating has a very long life expectancy which can reach up to 20 years with very little degradation in performance.

PP70 can block the Ultraviolet (UV) waves from passing through the coating, PP 70 only lets 70-80% of the visible light and 70% of the infrared to pass through it, which will reject up to 30-38% as can be seen from table (3) and Figure (5).

Table (3): Datasheet of PP 70. (LLumar, 2018)

Performance Data	Platinum silver 70 (PP 70)
Solar energy transmission	53%
Solar energy rejection	20%
Solar energy absorption	27%
Visible light transmission	70%
Visible light rejection	18%
Ultraviolet transmission	<1%
Total solar energy rejection	38%
Thickness without linear	43 μ

Figure (5): PP 70 effect on the solar spectrum. (Green Rhino Energy,2016)

2.3 Theoretical Tests

2.3.1 CoDePro

As the result found was based on experimental data, a simulation software was used to validate the result, CoDePro was the selected software, the software was developed by university of Wisconsin- Madison, CoDePro was used to perform the efficiency test with different flow rates and the overheating tests theoretically to be able to compare it with the experimental result. As can be seen in Figure (6), the test conditions, collector dimensions, cover and plate details, insulations details and the fluid details were all entered in the software.

Figure (6): CoDePro program.

The software has all the required equations and constants coded in it, the efficiency equation and the performance parameters such as stagnations temperature were found by doing iterations in the software itself, iterations helps to get very accurate result from the tests, which is the main advantage of this software.

A comparison between the experimental result with the theoretical one was done in the software itself by entering the experimental data and entering the efficiency equation in the software.

2.3.2 MATLAB

The output of the experimental test needed to be filtered out and analyzed to be able to get sensible and accurate representation of the result, first MATLAB code was built to help us choose the perfect points from the efficiency tests to be able to draw the efficiency curve for the three different flow rates, chosen points must be perfect to be able to draw the efficiency performance curve based on temperature difference ($T_{avg} - T_{amb}$), and the second MATLAB code was built to represent the experimental data in graphical forms.

3. Result

In this section, the experimental result for the coating tests and the theoretical result will be represented. Due to the limitation of this report, significant result will be shown in this section and the other results will be in the appendix.

3.1. Experimental tests

3.1.1. Before Applying the Coating

3.1.1.1. Efficiency Test

The efficiency test was done on the FPC before putting the coating for three different flow rates, in this section we will represent the high flow rate only because of the limitation.

As can be seen in Figure (7), the volumetric flow rate is on the top right and it was about 4 l/m in this test, the FPC was running for an hour without the coating, the efficiency average was about 55% as can be seen in bottom right of the figure, the inlet temperature is in blue on the top left of the figure and the outlet temperature is in red on the same graph, the ambient temperature is the green line, the last figure on the bottom left is the solar irradiance which was about 500 W/m².

Figure (7): Data taken from the system before the coating (4 l/m).

This data was before applying the coating on the FPC which showed all the important parameter that can be affected and changed by the coating.

The second graph shown in Figure (8) was made by selecting the right points from the data by using MATLAB, this graph represents the efficiency curve based on temperature difference of the FPC during high volumetric flow rate (4 l/m), the points were put in the graphs and a linear fitting line was made, the starting efficiency was about 76%.

Figure (8): Efficiency curve at 4 l/m (before coating).

3.1.1.2. Overheating Test

In the this test the FPC was left for three days without demand and without flow of water, this test was made to find out the stagnation temperature of the FPC and how the FPC react to overheating that's why this experiment was focused on the solar noon time when it is most likely the system will experience overheating, the inlet was closed and the pump was switched off during the whole time. The overheating on the second day will be only represented in this section due to report limitation.

As can be seen in Figure (9), the inlet temperature is the blue line on the top left, the outlet temperature is red and the green line is the ambient temperature, on the top left is the absorber temperature, the maximum absorber temperature (Stagnation temperature) was found to be almost 135°C , the last graph is the irradiance.

Figure (9): Data taken during the overheating test before adding the coating.

3.1.2. After Applying the Coating

3.1.2.1 Efficiency Test

The coating (PP70) was applied on top of the glass by using certain tools, after that the same efficiency test was done with three different flow rates, but again the high flow rate will be discussed in this section due to limitation and the other two will be in the appendix.

The FPC collector was again ran for one hour and important data was collected from the system to see how the system will react to the coating. As can be seen in figure (10), the flow rate is 4 l/m (same as before), the average efficiency was 48%.

Figure (10): Data taken from the system after the coating (4 l/m).

Also, the efficiency curve based on temperature difference was made by using MATLAB by selecting the correct points from the data. As can be seen in Figure (11), the starting efficiency is about 70%.

Figure (11): Efficiency curve at 4 l/m (after coating).

3.2.1.2 Overheating test

After applying the coating, overheating test was done again on the FPC for another 3 day and solar noon time was focused and examined to see how the coating will change the stagnation temperature, the second day will be presented here only in this section. As can be seen in figure (12) the stagnation temperature (maximum absorber temperature) was 108 °C.

Figure (12): Data taken during the overheating test before adding the coating

3.2. Theoretical results

To get the theoretical result and to be able to validate and compare it with the experimental results, CoDePro was used, all dimensions and important data was entered in the software to be able to create similar scenarios to the experimental tests. The first tests done was the efficiency tests for 3 different flow rates and the second test was the overheating test.

3.2.1. Before the Coating

3.2.1.1. Efficiency Test

All the necessary parameters were inserted into the software to do the efficiency test, after that the efficiency graphs were made for each flow rate in the program to be able to compare it with the same efficiency graphs from the experiments.

The efficiency graph was made in the program by doing iterations and using all the important equations that is coded in the software. As can be seen in Figure (13) the starting efficiency for 4 L/m, 3.2 L/m and 1.1 L/m was found to be 76.25 %, 76 % and 75.3 % respectively.

Figure (13): Efficiency curve from CoDePro before coating.

3.2.1.2. Overheating Test

The overheating test was done also in the software, water flow was set to zero and the stagnation temperature (maximum temperature of the absorber plate) was calculated, the stagnation temperature was found to be 141.3° C and for the glass it was 54.87°C.

3.2.2. After the coating

After entering the PP70 properties in the program, the efficiency test and the overheating test was done again to see how the FPC will react to the coating theoretically and validate the experimental results.

3.2.2.1. Efficiency test

Same test was applied after adding the coating for the same 3 flow rate. As can be seen in figure (14), the efficiency curve was generated using the program and the initial efficiency for 4 L/m, 3.2 L/m and 1.1 L/m was found as 60.15 %, 59.9 % and 59.05 % respectively.

Figure (14): Efficiency curve from CoDePro before coating.

3.2.2.2. Overheating Test

Overheating test was done in CoDePro by applying the coating details in the software and putting it on the glass cover. the stagnation Temperature of the coating and the cover glass is about 47°C and for the absorber plate was 114°C .

4. Discussion

Table (4): Main experimental Result.

Experimental Result	Before the Coating	After the Coating	Percentage Difference
Avg Efficiency at 4 l/m	53.44 %	46.45 %	13.08 %
Avg Efficiency at 3.2 l/m	61.63 %	52.3 %	15.13 %
Avg Efficiency at 1.1 l/m	58.11 %	50.2 %	13.61 %
Stagnation Temperature	134.29 ° C	108.7 ° C	19.05 %
Time needed to overheat (starting from 9 AM)	3.09 hours	3.996 hours	29.32 %
Highest Efficiency from the Efficiency Curve at 4 l/m (starting Efficiency)	76 %	70 %	7.8 %
Highest Efficiency from the Efficiency Curve at 3.2 l/m (starting Efficiency)	73 %	65 %	10.9 %
Highest Efficiency from the Efficiency Curve at 1.1 l/m (starting Efficiency)	72 %	60 %	16.6 %

Table (5): Main theoretical result.

Theoretical Result	Before the Coating	After the Coating	Percentage Difference
Stagnation Temperature	141.3 ° C	114 ° C	19.32 %
Highest Efficiency from the Efficiency Curve at 4 l/m (starting Efficiency)	76.25 %	60.15 %	21.1 %
Highest Efficiency from the Efficiency Curve at 3.2 l/m (starting Efficiency)	76 %	59.9 %	21.8 %
Highest Efficiency from the Efficiency Curve at 1.1 l/m (starting Efficiency)	75.3 %	59.05 %	21.2 %

A comparison table was made to summarize the work in a way to make discussion easier as can be seen in table (4) and in table (5). On the experimental side when it comes to the efficiency, we notice that the coating made the efficiency decrease in different flow rate the average efficiency drop was 15%, which is understandable because the coating reduce the heat coming from the sun (the coating will block the UV and 30% of the IR and the visible light) which will make the heating process slower and that will make the efficiency decrease.

The temperature difference between the inlet and the outlet was reduced after using the coating and referring to Equation (1) when the temperature difference ΔT is reduced the useful heat Q_u will be reduced which will lower the efficiency. And as can be seen the efficiency drop was almost the same in the 3 different flow rates.

When it comes to the absorber collector maximum temperature (Stagnation temperature) was reduced by 19.05%, the reduction in the temperature will prevent damaging the plastic components in the system and prevent plastic deformation in absorber and other components, also the amount of steam that left the system through the pressure relief valve is less than before, so money is saved and no need to refill the system especially if the system was pressurized.

The efficiency curve moved down a little which lowered the starting efficiency in all the 3 different flow rates as shown in Figure (15), which is expected because the efficiency curve is based on temperature difference $(\frac{T_{in} + T_{out}}{2} - T_{ambient})$ all divided by the solar irradiance G_T , so for the same solar irradiance, ambient temperature and mean temperature as before the coating it will give lower efficiency because of the lower temperature uplift.

Also, as noticed from the efficiency curves in figure (11) and (8) in the experiment part, all the points were in the left side of the graph because of the high ambient temperature.

Figure (15): Experimental Instantaneous Efficiency of the FPC (4 l/m). (only 4 l/m efficiency curve is shown because of the limitation)

The stagnation temperature decreased after applying the coating which was because of the less solar energy passing the glass and hitting the absorber plate, which directly solves the main problem (overheating problem) of the dissertation paper.

It was noticed that the time needed for the system to reach the overheating temperature was higher than before because the coating absorb and block some of the solar radiation and that will delay the overheating process, and will delay the time needed to reach the stagnation temperature, also the time needed for the absorber to lose their heat was longer than before because the coating will block some of the infrared (IR) waves that will be emitted by the absorber while cooling down at night, so less heat lost by radiation from the FPC.

Another physical benefit for the coating that was noticed that the glass is now more resistible to scratches which will give the glass longer life time and will slow the degeneration, another physical benefit was seen during the experiments is that the coating was a little more resistible to soil and dust because the surface of the coating is more slippery (which will it harder for the dust to stick) and that is because the surface finishing of the coating is better than the glass, even during the cleaning process, it was easier to clean the glass with the coating on top of it.

Now when it comes to theoretical side, the efficiency curve decreased similarly to the experimental result but in theoretical result the decrease was about 21% which is more than the experiment as can be seen in Figure (16).

Figure (16): Theoretical Instantaneous Efficiency of the FPC (4 l/m).

The drop was more than the experiment because, in the software it was assumed that the coating was applied perfectly on the glass but in reality, the coating is hard to put it on the glass without bubbles or spots that the coating was not steaky enough to the glass, so the coating won't preform and block heat perfectly in reality.

And the second reason why that the coating won't block all the UV and 30% of IR and VL is because the coating will only block the waves under certain weather conditions (wind speed, RH, diffused to direct radiation ration.... etc.) so in reality the weather won't be the same to make the coating work well.

The theoretical stagnation temperature also decreased after applying the coating just like the experiment result, the drop was 19% between in stagnation temperature before the coating and after the coating which is the same as the experiment result.

As can be seen form tables (4) and (5), there is a good agreement between calculated efficiency from the experiment and the efficiency from the software before and after the coating, to know how much the experiment disagrees with the actual calculation we will use standard deviation of residuals or Root-mean-square error (RMSD), it is defined as:

$$RMSD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (X_{EXP} - X_{SOFTWARE})^2}{N-1}} \quad (5)$$

The RMSD between the efficiency curve from the software with the efficiency points from the experiment without coating at flow rates of 4 l/m, 3.2 l/m and 1.1 l/m are 2%, 5% and 7% respectively. On the other hand, the RMSD between the efficiency points from experiment and the efficiency equation from the software at same flow rates with the coating are 9%, 7% and 3% respectively.

So PP70 directly solve the overheating problem which is very common in hot weathers just like UAE, and when It comes to economics the coating price (66 AED/m²) is a small percentage of the collector price and it is worth it to put it on every collector. The coating has the potential to be commercialized.

5. Conclusion

In this paper overheating in FPC problem was tackled by using PP70 coating, the coating was evaluated theoretically and experimentally. If the volumetric flow rate is increasing the starting efficiency is increasing and the efficiency curve slope is decreasing, which gives less heat loss coefficient and better performance.

Experimentally, after applying the PP70 the starting efficiency of the collector dropped 15% on average and the stagnation temperature also dropped 19.05%. Theoretically, the starting efficiency dropped 21% on average and the stagnation temperate decreased by 19.32%, and Root-mean-square error confirmed that the experimentally measured efficiency agreed with the calculated efficiency at different flow rates.

The PP70 coating will helped the solar collector to prevent severe damages from the overheating by dropping the stagnation temperature 19% and delay the overheating. Also, it enhanced the physical performance of the glass in terms of resisting soil and scratches. The stagnation temperature dropped from 132.29° C to 108.7° C after the coating. The numerical result was very close to the experimental result in both the efficiencies and the stagnation temperatures. The PP70 directly solve the overheating problem.

Appendix

As can be seen in figure (17) the temperature uplift is about 6 °C and the average efficiency is about 61.63%, the flow rate averaged out to be about 3.2 l/m, the reason that the flow meter has a lot of oscillation because of the system has maybe bubbles or dirt which cause the disturbance but it was confirmed that the pump was set to 3.2 l/m.

Figure (17): Data collected from efficiency test (3.2 l/m).

The efficiency curve based on temperature difference was made using MATLAB by selecting perfect points, the starting efficiency was about 73% as can be seen in figure (18).

Figure (18): Efficiency curve for 3.2 l/m flow rate.

In low flow rate the temperature left was about 8 °C and the average temperature was 58.11%, the average flow rate was 1.1 l/m as can be seen in figure (19).

Figure (19): Data collected from efficiency test (1.1 l/m).

In the efficiency curve the starting efficiency was about 72% as shown in Figure (20).

Figure (20): Efficiency curve for 1.1 l/m flow rate.

The overheating in the software can be seen in Figure (21) before and after the coating.

Figure (21): Overheating in software, (a) stagnation temperatures before coating. (b) stagnation temperatures after coating.

References

- Alkhatib, H. (2025). Enhancing Performance and Mitigating Overheating in Flat Plate Solar Collectors: A UV- Selective Coating Approach - Experimental Analysis. *Results in Engineering*, 103766. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2024.103766>
- Alkhatib, H., & Lemarchand, P. (2025). Assessing thermal performance: An experimental study on U-value variability in building fabric elements. *Results in Engineering*, 25, 103730. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2024.103730>
- Alkhatib, H., Lemarchand, P., Norton, B., & O'Sullivan, D. (2023a). Optimal Temperature Actuated Control of a Thermally Insulated Roller Blind. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4372791>
- Alkhatib, H., Lemarchand, P., Norton, B., & O'Sullivan, D. T. J. (2021). Deployment and control of adaptive building facades for energy generation, thermal insulation, ventilation and daylighting: A review. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 185(August), 116331. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2020.116331>
- Alkhatib, H., Lemarchand, P., Norton, B., & O'Sullivan, D. T. J. (2023b). Comparative simulations of an electrochromic glazing and a roller blind as controlled by seven different algorithms. *Results in Engineering*, 101467. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2023.101467>
- Alkhatib, H., Lemarchand, P., Norton, B., & O'Sullivan, D. T. J. (2023c). Comparison of control parameters for roller blinds. *Solar Energy*, 256, 110–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2023.03.042>
- Alkhatib, H., Lemarchand, P., Norton, B., & O'Sullivan, D. T. J. (2023d). Optimal temperature-actuated control of a thermally-insulated roller blind. *Building and Environment*, 244, 110751. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2023.110751>
- Alkhatib, H., Norton, B., Gavin, D., & Lemarchand, P. (2024). Assessing thermal performance: Dataset from an experimental study on U-value variability. *Data in Brief*, 57, 111067. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2024.111067>
- Alkhatib, H., Norton, B., O'Sullivan, D. T. J., & Lemarchand, P. (2025). Calibration of Solar Pyranometers for Accurate Solar Irradiance Measurements: A Data Set from the Pre- and Post-Calibration Process. *Data in Brief*, 111402. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2025.111402>
- Alkhatib, H., O'Neill, N., Norton, B., Lemarchand, P., & O'Sullivan, D. T. J. (2025). Achieving operational synergy between different adaptive façade technologies. *Results in Engineering*, 26, 105000. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2025.105000>
- Omar, O. K., Alshwabkeh, M., & Alkhatib, H. (2025). Closed form solutions of bending Bi-directional functionally graded tapered beams using Euler and Timoshenko theories. *Results in Engineering*, 25, 104204. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2025.104204>

Fabio Struckmann (2008) *Analysis of a Flat-plate Solar Collector*, Dept. of Energy Sciences, Faculty of Engineering, Lund University, Available at:

http://www.lth.se/fileadmin/ht/Kurser/MVK160/Project_08/Fabio.pdf

(Accessed 12 August 2019)

Elimar Frank, Franz Mauthner, Stephan Fischer, (2015), *Overheating prevention and stagnation handling in solar process heat applications* Institut für Solartechnik SPF, Available at:

http://task49.iea-shc.org/Data/Sites/7/frank_iea_shc_task49_overheatingstagnationreport_approved_v-2-3.pdf

(Accessed 12 August 2019)

Ehrmann, N., Reineke-Koch, R., Föste, S. and Giovannetti, F. (2013) 'The influence of process parameters and coating properties of double glazing coated with transparent conducting oxides on the efficiency of solar-thermal flat-plate collectors', *Thin Solid Films*, 532, 132-140.

Llumar,(2018) Data sheet for Platinum silver 70 Available at:

<https://northamerica.llumar.com/automotive-film/types-of-automotive-film/metallized-window-tint> (Accessed 12 August 2019)

Green Rhino Energy, (2016), Intensity and Energy Available at:

<http://www.greenrhinoenergy.com/solar/radiation/characteristics.php> (Accessed 12 August 2019)

John, A. and William, A. (2013) *Solar Engineering of Thermal Processes* 4th ed., University of Wisconsin-Madison, Solar Energy Laboratory. Available at:

<file:///C:/Users/Mohammad/Downloads/SolarEngineeringofThermalProcesses4thEdition-GearTeam41.pdf> (Accessed 12 August 2019)

Ruzhu Wang and Xiaoqiang Zhai (2018) *Handbook of Energy Systems in Green Buildings*, springer. Available at: <https://link-springer-com.ezproxy1.hw.ac.uk/content/pdf/10.1007%2F978-3-662-49120-1.pdf>

(Accessed 12 August 2019)

Kalogirou, S.A. (2004) *Solar thermal collectors and application*. Department of Mechanical Engineering, Higher Technical Institute. Available at: <https://www-sciencedirect-com.ezproxy1.hw.ac.uk/science/article/pii/S0360128504000103>

(Accessed 12 August 2019)

A. Whillier, (1953), *Solar energy collection and its utilization for house heating*. ScD. Thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Available at: <https://dspace.mit.edu/handle/1721.1/11922> (Accessed 12 August 2019)

Imants Ziemelis, Liene Kancevica, Zanis Jesko, Henriks Putans (1995) *Latvia calculation of energy produced by solar collector*. University of Agriculture, Research Institute of Agricultural Machinery. Available at: http://tf.llu.lv/conference/proceedings2009/Papers/36_Imants_Ziemelis.pdf (Accessed 12 August 2019)

J.P. Roberts, M.J. Brandemuehl, J.D. Burch, K.M. Gawlik, Overheat protection for passive solar water heating systems using natural convection loops, in: *Proceedings of the Solar 2000, American Solar Energy Society Annual Conference, 16–21 June 2000, Madison, WI, USA*, pp. 273–278.

Stephens, R.B., (1981). Fluid optical switch for a solar collector, (New Providence, NJ) US patent 4270517 available at: patft1.uspto.gov/netacgi/nph-Parser?patentnumber=4270517 (Accessed 12 August 2019)

Akhtar, N. and Mullick, S. C. (1999) *Solar Energy*, 66(5), 349-354.

Akhtar, N. and Mullick, S. C. (2007) *Energy*, 32(7), 1067-1074.

Duffie and Beckman (2006) *Solar engineering of thermal processes*, 3rd ed. ed., Wiley.

Facao, J. (2015) *Solar Energy*, 120, 104.

Jilani, G. and Thomas, C. (2014) *Energy*, 70.

Paone, A., Geiger, M., Sanjines, R. and Schüler, A. (2014) *Solar Energy*, 110, 151-159.

Resch, K., Wallner, G. M. and Lang, R. W. (2008) *Macromolecular Symposia*, 265(1), 49-60.

Slaman, M. and Griessen, R. (2009) *Solar Energy*, 83(7), 982-987.

Soulayman, S. S. (1991) *Renewable Energy*, 1(3-4), 551-554.

Spychaj, S. (2012) *Polimery*, 57(11-12), 893.

Vaibhav Singh, V., Thakur, J., Agarwal, R., Vyas, G. and Sekhar Dondapati, R. (2018) *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 5(14), 28211-28220.

Wallner, G. M., Resch, K. and Hausner, R. (2008) *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 92(6), 614-620.

Weber, A., Schmid, A. and Resch, K. (2014) *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 131(4), n/a-n/a.

Wu, L., Gao, J., Liu, Z., Liang, L., Xia, F. and Cao, H. (2013) *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 114(C), 186-191.

Kalogirou, S.A. (2004) *Solar thermal collectors and application*. Department of Mechanical Engineering, Higher Technical Institute. Available at: <https://www-sciencedirect-com.ezproxy1.hw.ac.uk/science/article/pii/S0360128504000103> (Accessed 12 August 2019)